

The Jammu and Kashmir Reorganisation: Need and Effect (With Specific Reference to Article 370)

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Abstract

On 5th August 2019, the center government revoked Article 370 of the Constitution which gives special status to Jammu and Kashmir, and brought in the Jammu and Kashmir Reorganisation Bill 2019 splits the state into two Union Territories: Jammu and Kashmir with an Assembly and Ladakh. Broadly, these landmark changes include the effective abrogation of Article 370 of the Constitution of India and the reorganization of the State of Jammu and Kashmir. This paper outlines the legal measures adopted to effectuate these changes and then proceeds to examine their constitutional validity. The paper contends to know the need for the Jammu and Kashmir Reorganisation bill. And the changes that this revocation will bring. Has Article 370 worked in the manner it was envisaged to or has it succeeded in aggravating inequality within the state and in the larger context of India? These objectives are achieved through a process of a comprehensive review of literature, and analysis. The study has tried to build understanding and knowledge on the impact and need of this bill on local government and citizens of Kashmir by secondary research.

Introduction

It is said that by seeing the beauty of Kashmir once Mughal Emperor Jahangir said "Gar Firdaus bar-rue zamin ast, hami asto, hamin asto, hamin ast" which means 'If there is a heaven on earth, it is here, it is here, it is here. The Mughal Emperor was so impressed by the beauty of Kashmir that he would often say, if one has not visited this beautiful paradise, they are missing out on something worthwhile. Even the great Kalidasa said "The place is more beautiful than heaven and is the benefactor of supreme bliss and happiness. It seems to me that I am taking a bath in the lake of nectar here." Kashmir in Sanskrit means land desiccated from water. It is made up of two words 'Ka' which means 'water' and 'shimeera' implying desiccate. As per mythological tales in Hindu scriptures, it was the revered Sage Kashyap who drained an erstwhile lake to carve a place like Kashmir. The people of Kashmir are, considered to come into the valley and settle down there. Kashmir became the home for the Buddhists, the dwelling for the teaching of Vedanta, and the center for mystic Islam. Different dynasties brought different cultures and religions to Kashmir. The people of Kashmir call the valley Pirwaer and Rishiwaer, the adobe of Rishis and Sufis.

Today in this paradise of earth, there is a spread of mistrust and violence. Jammu and Kashmir have a long painful battle for peace and security. J&K has been most popular amongst intellectuals like academicians, historians, politicians, defense analysts, and media in the past few years. Instability, separatist movements, and terrorism in J&K are being characterized by India's

failure to complete the integration of states into the Union. There is a large battle of words on media screens but still, the question of security and peace has been left unanswered. J&K has been a battleground for years be it a border exercise or an off-the-ground confrontation. In recent years, a common narrative on J&K has been revolving around regular unrest in Kashmir Valley extended to Jammu which is evident by various stone pelting, terror attacks, and encounters between Indian security forces and separatists. Moreover, Pakistan's intention to annex the state forcefully and consistent promotion of terror activities in J&K and other states for its own interest has been a pain in the Arse for the future of J&K. The entire framework of terror and its network has the support of Pakistan which is being used for Pak-sponsored Proxy Wars like Uri, Pulwama, etc. Furthermore, youth is being misguided and compelled towards stone pelting and revolts, with a false perception of Jihad.

In order to better understand what the most feasible and effective solutions may be under the current scenario after ending Jammu & Kashmir's special status (Article 370 & 35A), we will explore solutions from the viewpoint of the various stakeholders. As we know Kashmir is home to a number of ethnic and religious groups, and any sustainable resolution would need to take into account the aspiration of all Kashmiris.

The specific objective of the study is to know the need for the Jammu and Kashmir Reorganisation bill. And the changes that this revocation will bring. Has Article 370 worked in the manner it was envisaged to or has it succeeded in aggravating

inequality within the state and in the larger context of India? These objectives are achieved through a process of a comprehensive review of literature, and analysis. The study has tried to build understanding and knowledge on the impact and need of this bill on local government and citizens of Kashmir by secondary research. For creating this knowledge base, secondary data analysis, and media reporting trends on Jammu and Kashmir have been analyzed.

Article 370 & Article 35A

Article 370 of the Constitution of India provides special autonomy to the state of Jammu and Kashmir. The erstwhile Article 238, pertaining to Part B states or former princely states was repealed by the 7th Constitutional Amendment in 1956 after the reorganization of Indian states. However, Article 370 overrode the provisions of Article 238 as special stipulations for Jammu and Kashmir. Article 370 has been controversial right from inception, with Dr. B.R Ambedkar as the principal drafter of the Constitution, having refused to draft the article owing to its biased unequal dispensations within the framework of a free India. The drafting was eventually done by Gopalaswami Ayyangar, who was a confidante of Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru and former aide of the Maharaja of Kashmir. It was initially meant to be temporary in nature; hence it was included in the Temporary and Transitional Provisions in Part XXI.

The imposition of Article 370 in the Indian Constitution providing 'Temporary Special Status' has been evident in the prolongation of the separatist environment. Basically, Article 370 provides that

the articles of the Indian Constitution dealing with the administration of the states in Indian territory are not applicable to Jammu and Kashmir. And the power of Parliament to make rules for the state is limited (only the Union and Concurrent list are applicable that too when declared by the president in consultation with the state government). Article 370 was enacted for a temporary period considering special conditions in the state of Jammu and Kashmir. Article 35A was incorporated into the Constitution in 1954 by an order of the then President Rajendra Prasad on the advice of the Jawaharlal Nehru Cabinet. The controversial Constitutional (Application to Jammu and Kashmir) Order of 1954 trailed the 1952 Delhi Agreement between Centre and J&K state, which extended Indian citizenship to the 'State subjects' of Jammu and Kashmir. Article 35A is a unique provision of the Constitution of India though it is a part of the Constitution, but does not figure among the articles of the constitution. It is not found after article 35 in the constitution but in Appendix I of the Indian constitution. Article 35A empowers the Jammu and Kashmir State Legislature to define the rights and privileges of the State's 'permanent residents and their special rights and privileges. It was specially formulated to protect the State subject laws that had already been defined under the Dogra ruler Maharaja Hari Singh's regime and notified in 1927 and 1932. Nevertheless, this Article which came into force in 1954 without any presence in between the articles had been bizarre to the public of India.

How Article 370 came about: A timeline, November 1, 1858- June 20, 1949 (From: August 6, 2019: The Hindu)

Stages in the creation of state Jammu and Kashmir. (Source: Google Maps)

The Jammu and Kashmir Reorganisation Bill

The Centre government revoked Article 370 of the Constitution which gives special status to Jammu and Kashmir and brought in the Jammu and Kashmir Reorganisation Bill 2019, which splits the state into two Union Territories: Jammu and Kashmir with an Assembly and Ladakh without one. And by ending Jammu and Kashmir's special status in the Indian Union, the government also extended all provisions of the constitution to the state and allowed all citizens to buy property and vote in the state. The Jammu and Kashmir Reorganisation Bill was passed by both houses of the Indian Parliament on 5 and 6 August and was assented, to by the Indian President, Ram Nath Kovind, on 9 August. This complex Bill, drafted secretly, was introduced without democratic consultation. It was preceded by the deployment of many thousand troops to Kashmir, ostensibly to protect against an un-named threat. The Amarnath Yatra, an annual Hindu pilgrimage, was suspended and pilgrims and tourists were instructed to leave Kashmir.

A curfew was imposed, local politicians were restrained, means of communication were cut and a media shutdown was enforced. This was a transformative act in a perpetually restive State, its purpose is to end preferential rights, and its outcome was a further step towards the Hinduisation of India. The Bill provides for the reorganization of the state of Jammu and Kashmir into the Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir and the Union Territory of Ladakh. The resolution was adopted by Lok Sabha with 351 members voting in its support and 72 against it, while one member abstained. The bill to create two UTs -- Jammu and Kashmir, and Ladakh -- was passed by 370 votes in favor and 70 against. The resolution and the bill were approved by Rajya Sabha on August 5, 2019. The Jammu and Kashmir Reorganisation Bill, 2019 was introduced in Rajya Sabha on August 5, 2019, by the Minister of Home

Affairs, Mr. Amit Shah. He introduced two bills and two resolutions regarding Jammu & Kashmir (J&K).

These are as follows:

1. Constitution (Application to Jammu & Kashmir) Order, 2019 {Ref. Article 370(1) of Constitution of India} – issued by President of India to supersede the 1954 order related to Article 370.
2. Resolution for Repeal of Article 370 of the Constitution of India {Ref. Article 370 (3)}.
3. Jammu & Kashmir (Reorganisation) Bill, 2019 {Ref. Article 3 of Constitution of India}.
4. Jammu & Kashmir Reservation (2nd Amendment) Bill, 2019.
5. So far, the Parliament had only residuary powers of legislation in Jammu and Kashmir. This included enacted of laws to prevent terror and secessionist activities, taxation on foreign and inland travel, and communication.

Key changes

The President had used his powers under Article 370 to fundamentally alter the provision, extending all Central laws, instruments and treaties to Kashmir. However, the drastically altered Article 370 will remain on the statute books.

1. While the Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir will have a legislature, the one in Ladakh will not.
2. The notification by the president has effectively allowed the entire provisions of the Constitution, with all its amendments, exceptions and modifications, to apply to the area of Jammu and Kashmir.
3. The Bill proposes wide powers to the Lieutenant Governor of the proposed Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir and makes it the "duty" of the Chief Minister of the Union Territory to "communicate" all administrative

decisions and proposals of legislation with the LG.

4. All Central laws and State laws of J&K would apply to the new Union Territories of J&K and Ladakh.
5. Assets and liabilities of J&K and Ladakh would be apportioned on the recommendation of a Central Committee within a year.
6. Employees of State public sector undertakings and autonomous bodies would continue in their posts for another year until their allocations are determined.
7. The police and public order is to be with the Centre.
8. The notification amends the expression "Constituent Assembly", contained in the proviso to clause (3) of Article 370, to mean "Legislative Assembly".

The issues due to Article 370 are as:

1. **Article 370 affects unity and integrity:** It wreaks havoc on the unity and integrity of the country as it creates boundaries for the people of J&K by providing them with separate constitution and rights. It builds emotional and psychological barriers between the people of Kashmir and the rest of India, thus fostering a psychology of separatism.
2. **Issues of rising militancy and separatism:** The separatist lobby in the state has used this barrier to build a mindset of alienation among the people. The poor and the down-trodden people of the state were exploited by the separatist leaders to keep this special status alive. It has led to rising militancy in the region. Most of youth take to stone pelting, remain unemployed and are devoid of welfare development.
3. **Violation of Right to Equality:** No outsider can settle in the state, own any property and cannot vote in the state. Article 35A had been used to define permanent residents. This violates the fundamental right to equality for Indian citizens and creates barriers for investment and thus development.
4. **Corrupt and radical administration:** The state administration had been completely subverted from within by the separatist leaders who had infiltrated into the system over a period of time. This has led to government resources being used to further promote the propaganda of separatists.
5. **Article 370 affects International image:** Existence of this statute is used by Pakistan and its proxies in the valley to mock at the very concept of 'India being one from Kashmir to Kanyakumari. This affects India's image on the international platform. It bars the people from outside the state to buy immovable and movable

property here, set any industry or manufacturing unit, while no other state bars any state subject of J&K to invest there, acquire land or set business establishment. It act as obstacle in attracting the flow of investment from big business houses which are running mega projects and giving employment to thousands of educated youth according to their academic, professional, skilled, and non-skilled capabilities. Unemployment in J&K has promoted militancy. A poor youth after completing education with limited resources, after sitting idle for long, gets easily lured by the people who push them into anti-national activities by giving few thousands of rupees. It is a source of gender bias in disqualifying women from the State of property rights.

The Bill provides for reorganisation of the state of Jammu and Kashmir into the Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir and Union Territory of Ladakh. The Bill reorganises the state of Jammu and Kashmir into:

1. The Union Territory of **Jammu and Kashmir with a legislature**, and
2. The Union Territory of **Ladakh without a legislature**.
3. The Union Territory of **Ladakh** will comprise **Kargil and Leh districts**,
4. The Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir will comprise the remaining territories of the existing state of Jammu and Kashmir.
5. The Union Territory of Jammu and Kashmir will be administered by the President, through an administrator appointed as the Lieutenant Governor. The Union Territory of Ladakh will be administered by the President, through a Lieutenant Governor appointed by him.

The Need and Effect

Articles 370 and 35A held back economic development in Jammu & Kashmir. There must be investment and job opportunities in Jammu and Kashmir. Articles 35A and 370 have been standing in the way of development. No one goes there to invest. Most of the manufacturing activity in the state has remained restricted to the state's inherent capacities in agriculture and handicrafts. Therefore, past policies need to be reviewed.

1. Rationale behind this move

1. Article 370 has prevented J&K to merge with India rather than being the basis of its merger.
2. Article 370 was seen as discriminatory on the basis of gender, class, caste, and place of origin.
3. Post the repeal of the Article 370, doors to private investment in J&K would be opened, which would in turn increase the potential for development there.

4. Increased investments would lead to increased job creation and further betterment of socioeconomic infrastructure in the state.
5. Opening of buying of lands would bring in investments from private individuals and multinational companies and give a boost to the local economy.

2. Development opportunity by abrogating Article 370

1. Women will enjoy greater rights as all the laws made at the center will be implemented without any hindrance.
2. SC, ST, and individuals from other backward communities in other regions would enjoy special benefits as the central laws for the welfare of these communities.
3. The financial benefits for central government employees, including security forces, like LTC, HRA, and more will be provided to those posted in Jammu and Kashmir.
4. The vacant posts in Jammu and Kashmir will be filled. This will benefit the youth and they will receive employment.
5. State companies as well as private companies will be encouraged to create jobs for the local youths in the state.
6. J&K and Ladakh have the potential to become the biggest tourist destination in the world.
7. Currently, there is no medical college, engineering college, or management institution anywhere in Ladakh. Now, new start-ups, businesses, and the government will create new infrastructure and boost development along with the creation of new jobs.

The people of Ladakh will be brought to mainstream Indian society. The increased tourism will bring significant revenue, which could be used to create additional social infrastructure. As with any bilateral treaty, the status or definition of the LoC can be legally altered only with the agreement of both India and Pakistan. The constitutional changes to Article 370 do not automatically make an impact on the status of the LoC. On a question over the impact of this constitutional change on the Pakistani side territory, the Indian home minister reiterated India's claim to the whole of Kashmir. However, a diplomatic response from the Ministry of External Affairs clarified that the changes do not affect either the LoC or the Line of Actual Control (the disputed border with China running through Ladakh). Given these, many see the LoC as merely continuing with an indefinite and harmful status quo, thus preventing a substantive resolution of the conflict. Due to the expected changes in demography and commercialization of the Leh region. Its unique ecological and cultural value may get affected. Since the region is prone to international disturbances

from China and Pakistan, a large portion of pasture land will be occupied by military personnel. This will affect the farmer's community. There is no evidence that coming under the direct control of the central government would certainly lead to greater development of the region. For instance, the level of development in Andaman and Nicobar is not very impressive. The autonomy of Ladakh's Autonomous Hill Development Council which was already on the decline will further reduce.

Conclusion

India has used Article 370 many times to extend provisions of the Indian Constitution to Jammu and Kashmir. This is the only way through which, by mere Presidential Orders, India has almost nullified the effect of Jammu and Kashmir's special status. The special status of Jammu and Kashmir was meant to end, but only with the concurrence of its people. Moreover, this was done after a massive military build-up and the house arrest of senior political leaders, and the communications shutdown reveals a cynical disregard for democratic norms. The significant move, in theory, opens up potential opportunities for development-led economic growth in the Union Territories of Jammu and Kashmir, and Ladakh.

There is also a need to change the situations of Jammu and Kashmir by introducing extensive developmental policies and providing equal rights to the society of J&K state. All the victims of the state may get justice for the removal of discriminatory provisions of Articles 370 and 35A. There are the women of J&K who choose to marry outside the state and in doing so, lose the right for their offspring to be state subjects. The migrants from West Pakistan came in 1947 and settled in Jammu Division and the Valmikies (Safai Karamcharies) who still suffer and looking forward to justice. Now there is a need to establish equality for the comprehensive growth of the state, so that the youth of the state may find job opportunities and gel with the citizens of India from other states. Thus, the move is bound to have a significant impact on the demography, culture, and politics of Jammu and Kashmir. Whatever its intent is in enabling the full integration of Jammu and Kashmir with India, this decision to alter the State's status could have unintended and dangerous consequences.

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